

Open Infrastructures for OA Books SIG (now WG)

Proposition put forward by OPERAS members OAPEN, DOAB, Jisc, Open Book Publishers, Thoth Open Metadata, SPARC Europe, Public Knowledge Project

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We propose the creation of a new OPERAS Special Interest Group (SIG) to bring together the growing landscape of **open, community-focused infrastructures that support open access (OA) book publishing**. The proposed Working Group will develop and support communication channels and engagement between the players in this increasingly complex network, enable increased exchange and interoperability between the different infrastructures, and seed new collaborations, projects and developments, potentially including new OPERAS services, both now and in the future.

Why is this WG needed?

There now exists a large variety of small and medium-sized community-focused, open infrastructure providers that each in their own way provide crucial services to the wider OA book ecosystem. To name but a few, these include the registration of DOIs via Crossref and DataCite, the Public Knowledge Project's Open Monograph Press, OAPEN and DOAB's aggregator services, the provision of fully open metadata and dissemination workflows for publishers via Thoth, and the community-led participatory funding streams established via the Open Book Collective that support the day-to-day running of participating infrastructures.

We believe that this landscape of open and community-focused infrastructures, if properly nurtured and connected with each other, has the potential to offer strong and efficient joint solutions to strengthen and develop open access book publishing across Europe and beyond. We also believe that, as community-focused infrastructures, they are well placed to undertake this work in ways that respect bibliodiversity and support local publishing cultures. Nonetheless, much of this open infrastructural activity so far remains focused on the provision of individual services—partly because making connections and establishing

coordination between organisations takes time and resources, which are much more scarce for smaller-scale, non-profit and community-based initiatives. Hence, we believe there is great untapped potential for collaboration and problem-solving between the many community-focused, open networks and infrastructures that now exist to support open access books in a number of areas, many of which have been identified by the PALOMERA project as recommendations for action. We believe that an OPERAS SIG would be ideally placed to create the forum and impetus to enable this work to take place on an ongoing basis.

What work has been done already?

In the context of the Arcadia- and Research England-funded *Copim Open Book Futures* project (2023-26), we have, as part of a wider group, begun a [dedicated mapping and outreach exercise](#) to try to identify the manifold connections and relationships between those open, not-for-profit, community-owned infrastructures, with a particular focus on OA book publishing. This has been motivated by a shared curiosity to find out more about the manifold interconnections between the infrastructures themselves, while also considering the outward-facing links and connections to other digital infrastructure not-for-profits that—although not primarily engaged in book publishing—also provide key structural components and resources to the infrastructural ecosystem underpinning our digital publishing efforts. To list just a few examples, infrastructures such as Crossref (provision of DOIs) or Zenodo (generalist archiving of all kinds of digital content) come to mind.

From that starting point, more conversations took place that pointed to a wider need to facilitate collaborative exchange between these open, community-led stakeholders, to actively coordinate our individual efforts towards a more joined-up, collective and open response to the needs of OA book publishing.

This culminated in a workshop at the 2024 OPERAS conference, during which we presented this initial work and engaged the wider OPERAS network in the emerging conversations about how to bring these networks and infrastructures closer together. OPERAS, as a stable network of international stakeholders active in the field of open access, with shared values, was mentioned by a significant number of attendants as a potential facilitator of this work, and the idea of proposing a Special Interest Group (SIG) as the home of those conjoined mapping and networking efforts was welcomed by all participants.

Hence, we **propose the formal inception of a new “Open Infrastructures for OA Books” Working Group.**

Proposed main tasks of the WG

- As an initial step, to continue the data collection process by maintaining and further developing the interactive map at <https://kumu.io/flavoursofopen/oa-books-landscape-overview#map>
- This map is to be used as a tool to support the ultimate goal of the SIG: to reach out, engage and coordinate exchanges between open, community-focused infrastructures on an international scale to develop new collaborations and, potentially, new services for OA books.
- To engage with all interested stakeholders (both within the OPERAS Assembly of the Commons and outside the current OPERAS network) to identify the key challenges that prevent collaboration between open infrastructures that support OA books, and to explore opportunities to work together to address these: for example, opportunities to address and extend the recommendations provided by the PALOMERA project.
- To collaboratively investigate and communicate these opportunities and challenges, so they are better understood across the OPERAS network and beyond.
- To coordinate activities and solutions to these opportunities and challenges that enable the creation of open, innovative, robust and efficient services and outcomes.
- To develop ideas for future OPERAS services that might be particularly suitable to support community-led OA book publishing, including Diamond OA for books, and be of interest to diverse stakeholders including publishers, funders, authors etc.
- To facilitate outreach to new stakeholders, with the long-term goal of establishing a global community of open infrastructure providers united around the common aim of supporting open, inclusive and community-led open access book publishing.

How the proposed WG fits within the OPERAS network

Organisations that have expressed interest in supplying members of the proposed SIG:

- OPERAS members: OAPEN, DOAB, Jisc, Thoth Open Metadata, Open Book Publishers, SPARC Europe, Public Knowledge Project
- OPERAS SIG: The Open Access Books Network
- Non-OPERAS member: Open Book Collective (currently applying for OPERAS membership)

The proposed new Working Group would also interrelate closely with, among others, the Tools & Platforms SIG, the Open Access Books Network SIG and the Open Access Business

Models SIG (which to date has mostly focused on books), seeking to strengthen collaboration between the SIGs and increasing OPERAS's value as a hub for activity and knowledge on issues related to open access books.

The Working Group would engage with the variety of OPERAS Services to explore their applicability to the SIG's core focus of open, not-for-profit and community-led open access book publishing infrastructures. OPERAS Services that immediately stand out in that respect include PRISM, GoTriple, Metrics, and Pathfinder, and we envision that the SIG could be actively involved in scoping and developing future OPERAS Services.

We believe that this is necessary, continuous and long-term work, as coordination efforts need to be upheld to ensure the ongoing engagement of stakeholders. The landscape of Diamond open access book publishing is beginning to emerge in a more concerted fashion, and we believe a strong, values-led voice from community stakeholders is necessary to avoid the problems we have seen in the world of journal publishing.

Conclusion

We believe that this proposed Working Group has the potential to support exciting new developments in the field of open access book publishing, and that the proposed focus on open infrastructure is essential to accelerate these developments in a strategic and aligned way.